

**LINEAR COMBINATIONS OF TWO POLYGONAL NUMBERS
THAT TAKE INFINITELY OFTEN A SQUARE VALUE**

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Received: 3/17/20, Revised: 9/28/20, Accepted: 11/17/20, Published: 12/4/20

Abstract

Using basic properties of the Pell equation and the theory of congruences, we investigate the question of when a linear combination of two different types of polygonal numbers is infinitely often a perfect square. Let $P_k(x)$ denote the x -th k -gonal numbers. We give sufficient conditions about m, n such that the Diophantine equation

$$mP_p(x) + nP_q(y) = z^2$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions (x, y, z) , where $p \geq 3, q \geq 3$.

1. Introduction

A polygonal number [3] is a positive number, corresponding to an arrangement of points on the plane, which forms a regular polygon. The x -th k -gonal number [3, p. 5] is

$$P_k(x) = \frac{x((k-2)(x-1) + 2)}{2},$$

where $x \geq 1, k \geq 3$. There are many papers about the polygonal numbers and many properties of them have been studied, we can refer to the first chapter of [4] and D3 of [7].

In 2005, Bencze [1] raised a problem: determine all positive integers n for which $1 + \frac{9}{2}n(n+1)$ is a perfect square. In 2007, Le [11] showed that all positive integers n which make the form $1 + \frac{9}{2}n(n+1)$ to be a perfect square were given by

$$n = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{6} (a^{2k+1} + b^{2k+1}) - 1 \right),$$

¹This research was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 11501052), Younger Teacher Development Program of Changsha University of Science and Technology (Grant No. 2019QJCZ051), and Hunan Provincial Key Laboratory of Mathematical Modeling and Analysis in Engineering (Changsha University of Science and Technology).

where $a = 3 + \sqrt{8}, b = 3 - \sqrt{8}$, and $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. In 2011, Guan [6] proved that all positive integers n which make the form $1 + \frac{4n(n+1)s^2}{s^2-1}$ to be a perfect square were given by

$$n = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2s} (a^{2k+1} + b^{2k+1}) - 1 \right),$$

where $a = s + \sqrt{s^2 - 1}, b = s - \sqrt{s^2 - 1}$, and s is a positive odd integer with $s > 1, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. In 2013, Hu [8] used the theory of the Pell equation to study the positive integer solutions of the Diophantine equation

$$1 + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2,$$

where

$$n = \begin{cases} \frac{t^2 \pm 1}{2}, & t \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \quad t \geq 3, \\ \frac{t^2 \pm 2}{2}, & t \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \quad t \geq 2, \\ \frac{t(t-1)}{2}, & t \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

In 2019, Peng [12] showed that if $2n$ is not a perfect square, then the Diophantine equation $1 + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Meanwhile, she studied the Diophantine equation

$$mP_3(x - 1) + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2,$$

where $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and proved that when $\frac{m(m+1)}{2} = u^2, n = 1$, there exist infinitely many pairs (a, b) of integers such that $mP_3(x - 1) + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2$ has integer parametric solutions $(t, at + b, u(ct + d))$, where t is a positive integer greater than 1. Moreover, she got two general results:

- 1) If $2(m + n)$ is not a perfect square, $r \in \mathbb{Z}$, and the Pellian equation

$$X^2 - 2(m + n)Z^2 = \left(\frac{m + n}{2} \right)^2 - r^2 mn$$

has a positive integer solution (X_0, Z_0) satisfying

$$X_0 - rn + \frac{m + n}{2} \equiv 0 \pmod{m + n},$$

then the Diophantine equation $mP_3(x - 1) + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

- 2) Let u, v be integers with $u > \sqrt{2}v$, and u a positive even integer. When $m = (u^2 - 2v^2)^2, n = 8u^2v^2$, then the Diophantine equation $mP_3(x - 1) + nP_3(y - 1) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

In 2020, Jiang and Li [9] investigated the problem that the linear combination of two polygonal numbers is a perfect square, and they showed that if $k \geq 5, 2(k - 2)n$

is not a perfect square, and there is a positive integer solution (Y', Z') of $Y'^2 - 2(k - 2)nZ'^2 = (k - 4)^2n^2 - 8(k - 2)n$ satisfying

$$Y' + (k - 4)n \equiv 0 \pmod{2(k - 2)n}, \quad Z' \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

then the Diophantine equation $1 + nP_k(y) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions (y, z) . Moreover, they studied the Diophantine equation

$$mP_k(x) + nP_k(y) = z^2,$$

where $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and proved that when $\frac{ntr}{2}$ is a perfect square, where $t = r(k - 2) - 1$, there exist infinitely many pairs (a, b) of positive integers such that $mP_k(x) + nP_k(y) = z^2$ has integer parametric solutions $(x, ax + b, u(cx + d))$, where $k \geq 5$. Further, they obtained two general results:

1) If $k \geq 5$, $2(k - 2)(m + n)$ is not a perfect square, $r \in \mathbb{Z}$, and the Pellian equation

$$X^2 - 2(k - 2)(m + n)Z^2 = (k - 4)^2(m + n)^2 - 4(k - 2)^2mnr^2$$

has a positive integer solution (X_0, Z_0) satisfying

$$X_0 - 2(k - 2)nr + (k - 4)(m + n) \equiv 0 \pmod{2(k - 2)(m + n)}, \quad Z_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

then $mP_k(x) + nP_k(y) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

2) Let $k \geq 5$, $m = 2(u^2 - 4u - 4)^2$, $n = 2(u^2 + 4u - 4)^2$. If $2(k - 2)$ is not a perfect square, and the Pell equation $X^2 - 8(k - 2)(u^2 + 4)^2Z^2 = 1$ has a positive integer solution (U_0, V_0) satisfying $U_0 - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(k - 2)}$, then $mP_k(x) + nP_k(y) = z^2$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

In this paper, we continue the study of [9], and consider the positive integer solutions of the Diophantine equation

$$mP_p(x) + nP_q(y) = z^2, \tag{1}$$

where m, n are positive integers and $p \geq 3$, $q \geq 3$. The main results are as follows.

Theorem 1. *Let $m = (q - 4)^2(p - 2)t$, $n = (p - 4)^2(q - 2)rt$, for the following two cases: 1) $p = 3$, $q \geq 5$, $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; 2) $p > 4$, $q > 4$, $r \equiv -1 \pmod{p - 2}$. When $\frac{tr(r+1)}{2}$ is a perfect square, there exist infinitely many pairs (a, b) of positive integers such that Equation (1) has integer parametric solutions $(au + b, (p - 2)(q - 4)cu, w(du + e))$, where r, w are positive integers.*

Theorem 2. *If $p \geq 3$, $q \geq 3$ and $2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)$ is not a perfect square, $r \in \mathbb{Z}$, and the Pellian equation*

$$\begin{aligned} & X^2 - 2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)Z^2 \\ & = -4mn(p - 2)(q - 2)r^2 - 8mn(p - q)r + ((p - 4)m + (q - 4)n)^2 \end{aligned}$$

has a positive integer solution (X_0, Z_0) satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 - 2(q - 2)nr + ((p - 4)m + (q - 4)n) &\equiv 0 \pmod{2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)}, \\ Z_0 &\equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \end{aligned}$$

then Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

Theorem 3. For $p \geq 3$, $q \geq 3$, if $m + n$ is a perfect square, but $2mn(p^2(q - 2)m + q^2(p - 2)n)$ and $2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)$ are not perfect squares, then Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

Theorem 4. If $p \geq 3$, $q \geq 3$, $p \neq 4$, $q \neq 4$ and $2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)$ is not a perfect square, $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}$, and the Pell equation

$$U^2 - 2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)V^2 = 1$$

has a positive integer solution (U_0, V_0) satisfying

$$U_0 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)}, \quad V_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

then Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

Remark 1. When $p = q$, this is the case studied by Jiang and Li [9].

Remark 2. When $p = 4$, $q = 4$, this corresponds to a linear combination of two square numbers. Cohen [2, Corollary 6.3.6.] studied the general case

$$Ax^2 + By^2 = Cz^2,$$

and gave the general solutions, i.e., “assume that $ABC \neq 0$, let (x_0, y_0, z_0) be a particular nontrivial solution of $Ax^2 + By^2 = Cz^2$, and assume that $z_0 \neq 0$. The general solution in rational numbers to the equation is given by

$$\begin{cases} x = d(x_0(As^2 - Bt^2) + 2y_0Bst), \\ y = d(2x_0Ast - y_0(As^2 - Bt^2)), \\ z = dz_0(As^2 + Bt^2), \end{cases}$$

where $d \in \mathbb{Q}$, $s, t \in \mathbb{Z}$, and $\gcd(s, t) = 1$.”

2. Preliminaries

To prove the above results, we give the following lemmas.

Lemma 1 ([10]). Let D be a positive integer which is not a perfect square. Then the Pell equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = 1$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions. If

(U, V) is the least positive integer solution of the Pell equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = 1$, then all positive integer solutions are given by

$$x_s + y_s\sqrt{D} = (U + V\sqrt{D})^s,$$

where s is a positive integer.

Lemma 2 ([10]). Let D be a positive integer which is not a perfect square, N be a nonzero integer, and (U, V) be the least positive integer solution of $x^2 - Dy^2 = 1$. If (x_0, y_0) is a positive integer solution of $x^2 - Dy^2 = N$, then an infinitude of positive integer solutions are given by

$$x_s + y_s\sqrt{D} = (x_0 + y_0\sqrt{D})(U + V\sqrt{D})^s,$$

where s is a nonnegative integer.

Lemma 3 ([5]). Let D be a positive integer which is not a perfect square, m_1, m_2 be positive integers, and N be a nonzero integer. If the Pellian equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = N$ has a positive integer solution (u_0, v_0) satisfying

$$u_0 \equiv a \pmod{m_1}, \quad v_0 \equiv b \pmod{m_2},$$

then it has infinitely many positive integer solutions (u, v) satisfying

$$u \equiv a \pmod{m_1}, \quad v \equiv b \pmod{m_2}.$$

3. Proofs of the Theorems

Proof of Theorem 1. If $h(x, y) = mP_p(x) + nP_q(y)$, Equation (1) becomes $h(x, y) = z^2$. When

$$m = (q - 4)^2(p - 2)t, \quad n = (p - 4)^2(q - 2)rt,$$

let

$$x = au + b, \quad y = (p - 2)(q - 4)cu.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & h(au + b, (p - 2)(q - 4)cu) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(q - 4)^2(p - 2)^2t(a^2 + rc^2(q - 2)^2(p - 4)^2)u^2 \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{2}(q - 4)^2(p - 2)t((2(p - 2)b - (p - 4))a - (p - 4)^2(q - 2)rc)u \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{2}(q - 4)^2(p - 2)tb((p - 2)b - (p - 4)). \end{aligned}$$

Consider

$$g(u) = h(au + b, (p - 2)(q - 4)cu)$$

as a quadratic polynomial of u . If $g(u) = 0$ has multiple roots, then the discriminant of $g(u)$ is zero, i.e.,

$$a^2 - 2cr(q - 2)(2(p - 2)b - (p - 4))a - rc^2(q - 2)^2(4(p - 2)^2b^2 - 4(p - 2)(p - 4)b - (p - 4)^2r) = 0.$$

It implies

$$a = c(q - 2)(2(p - 2)br - (p - 4)r + 2\sqrt{\Delta}), \tag{2}$$

where $\Delta = (p - 2)r(r + 1)b((p - 2)b - (p - 4))$.

To find $a \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, we take $\Delta = W^2$. Then

$$\left(\frac{2(p - 2)b - (p - 4)}{|p - 4|}\right)^2 - r(r + 1)\left(\frac{2W}{|p - 4|r(r + 1)}\right)^2 = 1.$$

Letting

$$X = \frac{2(p - 2)b - (p - 4)}{|p - 4|}, \quad Y = \frac{2W}{|p - 4|r(r + 1)}, \tag{3}$$

we obtain the Pell equation

$$X^2 - r(r + 1)Y^2 = 1. \tag{4}$$

It is easy to see that the pair $(X_0, Y_0) = (2r + 1, 2)$ is the fundamental solution of Equation (4). So an infinitude of positive integer solutions of Equation (4) are given by

$$X_s + Y_s\sqrt{r(r + 1)} = \left(2r + 1 + 2\sqrt{r(r + 1)}\right)^{s+1}, \quad s \geq 0.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{cases} X_s = 2(2r + 1)X_{s-1} - X_{s-2}, & X_0 = 2r + 1, \quad X_1 = 8r^2 + 8r + 1, \\ Y_s = 2(2r + 1)Y_{s-1} - Y_{s-2}, & Y_0 = 2, \quad Y_1 = 4(2r + 1). \end{cases}$$

According to the above recurrence relations, we have

$$X_s - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \quad Y_s \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

From (2), we get $a_s = cr(q - 2)(p - 4)(X_s + (r + 1)Y_s)$. Hence, a_s is a positive integer.

1) When $p = 3$, $q \geq 5$, from (3), we obtain

$$b_s = \frac{X_s - 1}{2}, \quad W_s = \frac{r(r + 1)Y_s}{2}.$$

It is obvious that b_s and W_s are integers.

2) When $p > 4$, $q > 4$, we have

$$b_s = \frac{(p-4)(X_s+1)}{2(p-2)}, \quad W_s = \frac{(p-4)r(r+1)Y_s}{2}.$$

In view of b_s is an integer, we need $X_s+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(p-2)}$. If $r \equiv -1 \pmod{p-2}$, then $X_0+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(p-2)}$. According to the above recurrence relation, it is easy to prove that

$$X_s \equiv \begin{cases} -1 & \pmod{2(p-2)}, \quad s \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 1 & \pmod{2(p-2)}, \quad s \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Hence, when $s \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, we have

$$X_s + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(p-2)},$$

then b_s is a positive integer.

Therefore, Equation (1) becomes

$$\frac{tr(r+1)}{2}(du+e)^2 = z^2.$$

If $\frac{tr(r+1)}{2}$ is a perfect square, there exist infinitely many pairs (a, b) of positive integers such that Equation (1) has integer parametric solutions $(au+b, (p-2)(q-4)cu, w(du+e))$, where c, w are positive integers. \square

Example 5. When $p = 6, q = 5, r = 3, t = 6$, $\frac{tr(r+1)}{2} = 6^2$ is a perfect square, then $m = 24, n = 216$ and $a_0 = 270c, b_0 = 2$. Hence, Equation (1) has integer parametric solutions $(270cu+2, 4cu, 12(156cu+1))$, where c, u are positive integers.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $y = x + r, r \in \mathbb{Z}$, Equation (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)x - ((p-4)m - (2(q-2)r - (q-4)n)))^2 \\ & - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)(2z)^2 \\ & = -4mn(p-2)(q-2)r^2 - 8mn(p-q)r + ((p-4)m + (q-4)n)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Take $X = 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)x - ((p-4)m - (2(q-2)r - (q-4)n))$ and $Z = 2z$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & X^2 - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)Z^2 \\ & = -4mn(p-2)(q-2)r^2 - 8mn(p-q)r + ((p-4)m + (q-4)n)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By Lemma 1, if $2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)$ is not a perfect square, the Pell equation

$$X^2 - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)Z^2 = 1$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. By Lemma 2, if Equation (5) has a positive integer solution, it has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Assume that Equation (5) has a positive integer solution (X_0, Z_0) satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 - 2(q - 2)nr + ((p - 4)m + (q - 4)n) &\equiv 0 \pmod{2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)}, \\ Z_0 &\equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 3, Equation (5) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (X, Z) satisfying the above condition, which leads to infinitely many $x, z \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Then there are infinitely many $y = x + r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Hence, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions $(x, x + r, z)$. \square

Example 6. When $p = 6, q = 5, r = 1, m = 2, n = 1$, Equation (5) becomes

$$X^2 - 22Z^2 = -87. \tag{6}$$

It has a positive integer solution $(X_0, Z_0) = (1651, 352)$ satisfying

$$X_0 - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{22}, \quad Z_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

Note that $(u, v) = (197, 42)$ is the least positive integer solution of $X^2 - 22Z^2 = 1$. By Lemma 3, Equation (6) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (X, Z) satisfying the above condition, which leads to infinitely many $x, z \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Then there are infinitely many $y = x + 1 \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Hence, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions $(x, x + 1, z)$.

Proof of Theorem 3. By Theorem 2, it is sufficient to find a positive integer solution (X_0, Z_0) to Equation (5) satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 - 2(q - 2)nr + ((p - 4)m + (q - 4)n) &\equiv 0 \pmod{2((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)}, \\ Z_0 &\equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 &= pm + qn + 4mnt(p - q)((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n), \\ r &= -(pm + qn)t((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n), \end{aligned}$$

then Z_0 satisfies

$$Z_0^2 = 2mn(p^2(q - 2)m + q^2(p - 2)n)((p - 2)m + (q - 2)n)^2t^2 + 4(m + n). \tag{7}$$

If $m + n$ is a perfect square but $2mn(p^2(q - 2)m + q^2(p - 2)n)$ is not a perfect square, from Lemma 2, Equation (7) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (Z_0, t) . And suppose (Z'_0, t_0) is an arbitrary positive integer solution of Equation (7).

If $2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)$ is not a perfect square, by Lemma 1, the Pell equation $X^2 - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)Z^2 = 1$ has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Put (U_0, V_0) be the least positive integer solution of $X^2 - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)Z^2 = 1$. And Equation (5) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & X^2 - 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)Z^2 \\ &= -4nm(q-2)(p-2)(mp+nq)^2((p-2)m + n(q-2))^2t_0^2 \\ & \quad + 8nm(p-q)(mp+nq)((p-2)m + n(q-2))t_0 + ((p-4)m + n(q-4))^2, \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

which has a positive integer solution

$$(X_0, Z_0) = (pm + qn + 4mn(p-q)((p-2)m + (q-2)n)t_0, Z'_0)$$

satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} & X_0 + 2n(q-2)(mp+nq)((p-2)m + n(q-2))t_0 \\ & + (p-4)m + n(q-4) \equiv 0 \pmod{2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)}, \\ & Z_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2, an infinitude of positive integer solutions of Equation (8) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} X_s + Z_s\sqrt{2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)} &= \left(X_0 + Z_0\sqrt{2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)} \right) \\ & \quad \times \left(U_0 + V_0\sqrt{2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)} \right)^s, \quad s \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

From some calculations, we have

$$\begin{cases} X_{2s+2} = 2(2U_0^2 - 1)X_{2s} - X_{2s-2}, \\ Z_{2s+2} = 2(2U_0^2 - 1)Z_{2s} - Z_{2s-2}, \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 &= pm + qn + 4mn(p-q)((p-2)m + (q-2)n)t_0, \\ X_2 &= (2U_0^2 - 1)X_0 + 4((p-2)m + (q-2)n)U_0V_0Z_0, \\ Z_0 &= Z'_0, \\ Z_2 &= (2U_0^2 - 1)Z_0 + 2U_0V_0X_0. \end{aligned}$$

From $X = 2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)x - ((p-4)m - (2(q-2)r - (q-4)n))$ and $Z = 2z$, we have

$$x = \frac{X + (p-4)m + n(q-4)}{2((p-2)m + (q-2)n)} + n(q-2)(mp+nq)t_0, \quad z = \frac{Z}{2}.$$

Then

$$\begin{cases} x_{2s+2} = 2(2U_0^2 - 1)x_{2s} - x_{2s-2} - 8n(q-2)(mp+nq)((p-2)m+n(q-2))V_0^2t_0 \\ \quad + 4V_0^2((p-4)m+n(q-4)), \\ y_{2s+2} = x_{2s+2} - (mp+nq)t_0((p-2)m+n(q-2)), \\ z_{2s+2} = 2(2U_0^2 - 1)z_{2s} - z_{2s-2}, \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= 1 + nq((p-2)m+n(q-2))t_0, & x_2 &= 2V_0^2X_0 + 2U_0V_0Z_0 + x_0, \\ y_0 &= 1 - mp((p-2)m+n(q-2))t_0, & y_2 &= 2V_0^2X_0 + 2U_0V_0Z_0 + y_0, \\ z_0 &= \frac{Z_0}{2}, & z_2 &= \frac{(2U_0^2 - 1)Z_0 + 2U_0V_0X_0}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if $m+n$ is a perfect square, but $2mn(p^2(q-2)m+q^2(p-2)n)$ and $2((p-2)m+(q-2)n)$ are not perfect squares, then Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions $(x_{2s+2}, y_{2s+2}, z_{2s+2})$, where $s \geq 0$. \square

Example 7. When $p = 6, q = 5, m = 3, n = 1$ ($m+n = 2^2$), Equation (7) becomes

$$Z^2 = 572400t^2 + 16,$$

which has a positive integer solution $(Z_0, t_0) = (5296, 7)$. And Equation (5) becomes

$$X^2 - 30Z^2 = -839782391,$$

which has a positive integer solution

$$(X_0, Z_0) = (1283, 5296)$$

satisfying

$$X_0 + 14497 \equiv 0 \pmod{30}, \quad Z_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

Note that $(U_0, V_0) = (11, 2)$ is the least positive integer solution of $X^2 - 30Z^2 = 1$.

Hence, we have

$$\begin{cases} x_{2s+2} = 482x_{2s} - x_{2s-2} - 231952, & x_0 = 526, \quad x_2 = 243814, \\ y_{2s+2} = x_{2s+2} - 2415, & y_0 = -1889, \quad y_2 = 241399, \\ z_{2s+2} = 482z_{2s} - z_{2s-2}, & z_0 = 2648, \quad z_2 = 666394. \end{cases}$$

Thus, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions $(x_{2s+2}, y_{2s+2}, z_{2s+2})$, where $s \geq 0$.

Proof of Theorem 4. When $x = ut, y = vt, u, v, t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, Equation (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (2(u^2(p-2)m+v^2(q-2)n)t - (u(p-4)m+v(q-4)n))^2 \\ & - 2(u^2(p-2)m+v^2(q-2)n)(2z)^2 = (u(p-4)m+v(q-4)n)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Take

$$X = 2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)t - (u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n), \quad Z = 2z, \quad (9)$$

we get

$$X^2 - 2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)Z^2 = (u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n)^2. \quad (10)$$

By Lemma 1, if $2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)$ is not a perfect square, the Pell equation

$$U^2 - 2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)V^2 = 1 \quad (11)$$

has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Therefore, Equation (10) has infinitely many positive integer solutions. Suppose (U, V) is a positive integer solution of Equation (11), then $(|u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n|U, |u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n|V)$ is a positive integer solution of Equation (10). From (9), we have

$$t = \frac{|u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n|(U + 1)}{2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)}, \quad z = \frac{|u(p - 4)m + v(q - 4)n|V}{2}. \quad (12)$$

If Equation (11) has a positive integer solution (U_0, V_0) satisfying

$$U_0 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2(u^2(p - 2)m + v^2(q - 2)n)}, \quad V_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

then, by Lemma 3, Equation (11) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (U, V) satisfying the above condition, which leads to infinitely many $t, z \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Hence, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (x, y, z) satisfying $x = ut, y = vt$, where $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. \square

Example 8. When $m = n = 1, p = 6, q = 5, u = 2, v = 1$, Equation (11) becomes

$$U^2 - 38V^2 = 1.$$

By the theory of Pell equation, an infinitude of positive integer solutions of the above Pell equation are given by

$$U_s + V_s\sqrt{38} = (37 + 6\sqrt{38})^{s+1}, \quad s \geq 0.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{cases} U_s = 74U_{s-1} - U_{s-2}, & U_0 = 37, U_1 = 2737, \\ V_s = 74V_{s-1} - V_{s-2}, & V_0 = 6, V_1 = 444. \end{cases}$$

From (12), we have

$$t_s = \frac{5(U_s + 1)}{38}, \quad z_s = \frac{5V_s}{2}.$$

When $s \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, it is easy to see that

$$U_s + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{38}, \quad V_s \equiv 0 \pmod{2},$$

which leads to t_s, z_s are all positive integers. Hence, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions (x_s, y_s, z_s) satisfying $x_s = 2t_s, y_s = t_s$, where $s \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

Remark 3. When $m = M^2, n = 1$, for $p = 4, q \geq 3$, we can get some parametric solutions.

1) For $p = 4, q = 3$, Equation (1) becomes

$$(z - Mx)(z + Mx) = \frac{y(y + 1)}{2}.$$

Hence, we can take

$$\begin{cases} z - Mx = \frac{y + 1}{4Mr}, \\ z + Mx = 2Mry, \end{cases}$$

where r is a positive integer.

It leads to

$$x = \frac{8M^2r^2y - y - 1}{8M^2r}, \quad z = \frac{8M^2r^2y + y + 1}{8Mr}.$$

Take $y = 8M^2rt - 1$, we get

$$x = 8M^2r^2t - r - t, \quad z = M(8M^2r^2t - r + t).$$

2) For $p = 4, q = 4$, Equation (1) becomes

$$M^2x^2 + y^2 = z^2.$$

By the Pythagorean theorem, we have

$$x = k(u^2 - v^2), \quad y = 2Mkuv, \quad z = Mk(u^2 + v^2),$$

where $u > v$.

3) For $p = 4, q \geq 3$, Equation (1) becomes

$$(z - Mx)(z + Mx) = \frac{y((q - 2)(y - 1) + 2)}{2}.$$

Then we can take

$$\begin{cases} z - Mx = \frac{y}{4Mr}, \\ z + Mx = 2Mr((q - 2)(y - 1) + 2), \end{cases}$$

where r is a positive integer.

It leads to

$$x = \frac{(8M^2r^2(q-2)-1)y}{8M^2r} - (q-4)r, \quad z = \frac{(8M^2r^2(q-2)+1)y}{8Mr} - (q-4)Mr.$$

Take $y = 8M^2rt$, we have

$$x = 8(q-2)M^2r^2t - (q-4)r - t, \quad z = M(8(q-2)M^2r^2t - (q-4)r + t).$$

Hence, when $m = M^2$, $n = 1$, for $p = 4$, $q \geq 3$, Equation (1) has infinitely many positive integer solutions.

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